

Design and Implementation of English Pronunciation Game: The Demite

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Abstract— Current technological developments have a considerable influence on life. One of technology that has both positive and negative impacts is the widespread use of smartphones in Indonesia. Among these smartphone users, many of them are students. Due to the high level of addiction, there were not a few students who underestimated their obligations, namely international language learning, English language. To solve these problems, one of the solutions provided is to build games that can benefit the players. Based on several problems that have been explained previously, in this study a game called "The Demite" will be built which will provide solutions not only as a means of entertainment for the people of Indonesia, but also as a means of learning in pronunciation of English words. This game is a casual-horror genre with an Augmented Reality feature that requires the player to capture and fight ghosts by saying English words that appear with the right pronunciation. Based on the results of the implementation obtained, some of main scenario in the design of The Demite has been successfully implemented.

Keywords— *augmented reality, serious educational game, English, ghost, smartphone, android.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Current technological developments have a considerable influence on life. One of technology that has both positive and negative impacts is the widespread use of smartphones in Indonesia. Smartphone active smartphone users in Indonesia are currently more than 100 million people, making Indonesia the fourth largest smartphone active country in the world after China, India and America [1].

Among these smartphone users, many of them are students. Although many parents provide smartphones for them as a means of communication and appropriate entertainment, but not a few of these students who use smartpone as a medium of excessive entertainment. The results of research on the level of game play addiction in the area of Jatinangor Sumedang showed that as many as 38% of respondents included in the category of no addiction and 62% of respondents included in the category of addiction. Based on

these studies it was also concluded that the level of addiction occurred in school-age children [2].

Due to the high level of addiction, there were not a few students who underestimated their obligations, namely international language learning, English language. Based on the demographics issued by EF (English First), it was concluded that the level of English proficiency in Indonesian society is low, with an EF score. The EPI is 52.15, which is ranked 10th out of 20 countries in Asia, and is ranked 39th out of 80 world countries [3].

To solve these problems, one of the solutions provided is to build games that can benefit the players. In order to give an interesting impression to serious educational games, the impression of fun must be prioritized. For that, given a feature in the game that has become a game trend today. Based on Infoholic Research, the AR Gaming market is expected to reach \$ 284.93 billion in 2023, with a growth estimate of 152.7% during the 2017-2023 period. Improving AR integration into mobile devices, online population growth and innovation in technology in games, forcing many people to integrate AR into their traditional games. Increasing online gamers and internet penetration are some additional factors that contribute to market growth [4].

Based on several problems that have been explained previously, in this study a game called "The Demite" will be built which will provide solutions not only as a means of entertainment for the people of Indonesia, but also as a means of learning in pronunciation of English words. This game is a casual-horror genre with an Augmented Reality feature that requires the player to capture and fight ghosts by saying English words that appear with the right pronunciation. With this game, it is expected that players can learn how to speak English correctly.

II. ANALYSIS AND SYSTEM DESIGN

II.1 General Description of The Demite

II.1.1 Game abstract

The Demite, taken from Indonesian word Dedemit which means a spirited creature that haunts and disturb people [5], usually become a myth among the inhabitants of Indonesia's rural areas, villages even in the city's notoriously haunted areas, is a location-based augmented reality horror game inspired by Pokemon Go. The game utilizes the player's mobile device's GPS ability to locate, capture, battle mythical creatures, called The Demite, which appear on the screen as if they were at the same real-world location as the player. To catch *The Demite*, voice command in English is used, so this game is also used as a learning medium in speaking English.

II.1.2 Objectives to be achieved by the game

Learn to pronounce English words and sentences correctly.

II.1.3 Game justification

This game not only for entertainment purpose only, but also can help player to learn to pronounce English with fun

II.1.4 Core gameplay

Player needs to capture or kill ghosts and compete against other players.

II.1.5 Game features

Location-based, augmented reality, speech recognition.

II.1.6 Genre

Treasure hunt, casual, horror.

II.1.7 Number of players

Competitive multiplayer.

II.1.8 Target platforms

Android smartphone with a working internet connection and a rear camera.

II.1.9 Game theme

Horror game that introduce variety and uniqueness of Indonesian ghost.

II.1.10 History summary

The player woke up in the strangely dark and cold place somewhere in ITB, to bring the normal ITB back, he must expel all the ghosts roaming there.

II.1.6 Player characteristics

Anyone with minimum basic knowledge of English pronunciation.

II.2 Application Design of The Demite Game

II.2.1 General System Design

Video game *The Demite's* basically uses client server system that can be seen in Figure 1.

Figure 1 The Demite architecture design.

In client side, player uses smartphone's camera to view AR objects, and its microphone to detect player's voice using voice recognition. It also uses GPS to pinpoint player's location and Gyroscope to get device's orientation. While in server side, OpenStreetMap framework is used to get map data. SQLite and MySQL also used to retrieve user's data and word's database. The description of this client-server is not discussed in this study and will be discussed in related work, as this study is primarily discussed about game design of The Demite game.

II.2.2 Database Design

In this application, the database is used as a medium to store the data about users and ghost objects. In the project planning, the database used is MySQL.

This database will also record progress information related to the game, such as player's score, inventory and money. Player's score and money will be stored in *user_data* table, while player's inventory will be stored in *inventories* table. All data will be saved in server's database and will be retrieved the next time when player logs in.

Figure 2 The Demite database design.

II.2.3 Gameplay Design

When the first time a player opens a video game application, the player will be presented with a login view that will require the player to fill in a username and password. If the player does not have an account, then the player is required to create a new profile that will be used to log in.

After player successfully log in, player will be presented with *Map View* that displays the locations of ghost in the real world, with the player's avatar displays at the middle of the view. To move your avatar on the map, you need to change your location by walking in the real world. Your avatar represents your location, and as you move, you'll see your location move on your screen. Once you start moving in the real world, you'll be able to find ghosts. When a nearby ghost is spotted, the player can walk toward the ghost, and when the distance is close enough, the player will enter *Fight Mode*.

Figure 3. The Demite general gameplay Flowchart.

Fight mode shows when the player encounters a ghost, in this mode, the player can either capture or kill ghost. If the player wins the fight, or can capture the ghost successfully, then the score will increase, in contrary, if player lose the fight, then the score will decrease. After that, if the player wants to continue playing, the player can switch back to map view to search for other ghosts, otherwise the player can safely end the game's session.

In *fight mode*, the player can either capture or kill ghost. This mode displays in AR mode for more immerse feels. To capture ghost, first the player needs to spell the words on the screen. If the player spells it correctly, then ghost's Health Points (HP) will be reduced by certain amount. In contrary, if the words are spelled wrong, then player's fear bar will increase by certain amount. When fear bar is full, then the player cannot encounter with any ghost for certain amount of time.

Figure 4. *Fight mode* general interface

Fight mode has several objects shown in Figure 4. The interface description is as follows:

1. Ghost's profile
Shows the name of the ghost, remaining HP amount, and HP bar.
2. Ghost
Object representation of the ghost fought in this node.
3. Flying Words
Words are used to attack the ghost, when the player spelled this each word correctly, it will disappear, and ghost's HP will be reduced.
4. Player's profile
Shows player's icon, player's name, remaining fear amount, and fear bar.
5. Inventory
Shows the player's items that can be used to attack the ghost.

II.2.4 Ghosts Characteristics Design

There are many varieties of Indonesian ghosts, but in this game, only the most well-known ghosts are used. Some ghost can be captured and used as pet. Pet can help player in certain ways, such as steal money and items.

Pocong Pute – Ghost

Description: the soul of a dead person trapped in its shroud (*kain kafan*).

Attributes:

- Appearance: The dead body covered in white fabric tied over the head, under the feet, and on the neck.
- Health points: 20
- Ghost level: 1

Si Tuyul – Ghost

Description: It is a small child spirit invoked by a dukun (Indonesian shaman) from a dead human fetus using black magic.

Attributes:

- Appearance: Small child with a grey skin, bald, small hands, clouded eyes. Usually half-naked (only wear underpants).
- Health points: 40
- Ghost level: 2

Nyai Sundel Bolong – Ghost

Description: Sundel Bolong is the soul of a woman who died during childbirth and the baby came out from her back.

Attributes:

- Appearance: Woman with beautiful long hair and a long white dress. She has a large hole on her back.
- Health points: 60
- Ghost level: 3

Mba Kunti – Ghost

Description: Spirits of women who was raped when she was alive, then died while pregnant.

Attributes:

- Appearance: pale-skinned women with long black hair, red eyes, and white dress smeared in blood, but they are said to be able to take on a beautiful humanly appearance.
- Health points: 80
- Ghost level: 4

Mas Buto Ijo – Ghost, Pet

Description: Commonly asked for help by shamans and paranormal to bring great amount of money and wealth fast.

Attributes:

- Appearance: Tall and big, green skin, long hair.
- Health points: 100
- Ghost level: 5

Mbah Gondoruwo – Ghost

Description: Spirits of man who died and doesn't accept his own death.

Attributes:

- Appearance: Big human-like apes with a reddish black skin colour, his body is covered with thick hair growing all over the body.
- Health points: 120
- Ghost level: 6

III. IMPLEMENTATION AND TESTING

III.1 Implementation of Application

The hardware and software used to implement the client side and server side are as follows

Personal Computer : Intel Core i7-4710HQ CPU 2.50GHz, Memory 8 GB, Windows 10 Education.
 Smartphone Device : Xiaomi Redmi Note 5A, RAM 4GB, Nougat Android Version

III.1.1 Implementation of Interface

The following pictures will show the results of the implementation of The Demite video game application that has been done.

Figure 5. Login scene

Players can input their username and password first to play the game. If they don't have an account, they can sign up for a new one.

Figure 6. Fight mode with equipment slot.

Player can capture the ghost using items they have by tapping it in the inventory slot at the bottom of the screen. If the player doesn't need more item, they can buy it in the shop menu at the top corner of the screen.

IV. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the implementation obtained, some of main scenario in the design of The Demite has been successfully implemented. For further work, it is necessary to consider how to implement the unique characteristic of a ghosts and the development of how player can learn English pronunciation more efficiently.

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